

EDUCATING YOUNG PEOPLE IN THE SPIRIT OF MILITARY PATRIOTISM

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Annotation In this article, some tips and recommendations are given on raising young people in the spirit of military patriotism, encouraging them to be physically fit and loyal to the Motherland. The article is relevant and presented as important information for schools, colleges and educational institutions.

Keywords: patriot, military, student, youth, education, physical, mental, health

The development of society depends on the scope and logic of the reforms being implemented. Only those reforms that are carried out with deep and comprehensive thinking will make people's problems easier, their burdens lighter, their lives more comfortable, and find solutions to their problems. At the heart of the work being done, it is necessary to consider the long future along with the solution of today's problems.

In our country, the reforms in the education system, which did not take into account the development trends of the society, the demographic growth of the population, the aspirations of a significant group of young people, and the global technological processes, did not give the expected results. During his time, the problems increased and did not decrease.

The reforms being implemented under the leadership of President Shavkat Mirziyoyev are being carried out with deep consideration of demographic processes

and urbanization, the thinking of mankind, the growing political worldview, consciousness and culture of our people, and the public interest.

The development of society does not always develop evenly, because it is full of contradictions and contradictions on its way, but it overcomes these contradictions and contradictions with strong will and perseverance and completes its development path. The role and place of the country's leaders will be great in the selection process.

As the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev stated in his answer to the questions of the editor-in-chief of the newspaper "Yangi Uzbekiston", "It should be said openly that along with the great achievements in independent development, our path was not free from some mistakes and shortcomings. The processes aimed at abandoning the authoritarian regime and establishing a democratic society, the complex and dangerous period itself has put various problems and tasks before us. There were cases where our knowledge and experience, will and determination were sometimes enough to solve them successfully, and sometimes not."

If a leader cannot sense the turning point, society will stagnate. That is why historians recognize the role of a person in history and study it as a separate scientific subject. In this sense, our people have been thanking the leader. The key to any success is peace. Therefore, the services of the leader of the nation in the stable development of our society are great, and our people appreciate it.

The changes that took place as a result of reforms in the educational system, including higher education, are of great historical importance from a socio-political, legal, economic and spiritual point of view. The implemented reforms not only brought great positive changes in our country, but also brought the reputation of our country to a new level in the international arena. A number of regulatory documents have been adopted in this regard.

The President critically analyzed the shortcomings in education and showed ways to eliminate them.

Development of the educational system, increasing the qualifications and prestige of pedagogues in society, raising the spirituality of the young generation, adapting the spiritual and educational environment to the needs of the times, increasing the prestige of the teaching profession, training pedagogues of the new era, developing the science of pedagogy, innovative showed the need to pay serious attention to the introduction of education and information and communication technologies to education, and at the same time, to increase the salary of teachers and encourage them, great work has been done in these matters.

All conditions and opportunities are being created in higher educational institutions for the implementation of the state policy aimed at confidently solving all the issues put forward by modern science and industry.

As in any sustainable developing society there are mistakes and shortcomings, we must admit that we have them. The opportunity of young people to get higher education and realize their constitutional rights was limited to a certain extent. In the higher education reforms carried out in the next five years, such situations were completely put an end to and became a thing of the past.

The fate and future of every society and the people living in it are closely related to the education of young people, who are considered to be the leading forces determining the future development of the country. In this regard, the concept of educating young people in the spirit of patriotism was developed and approved, according to it

Young people who are ambitious, determined and act on this basis have a great role in determining the future of our country. Sufficient conditions are being created for the future owners to grow up well, master science, modern techniques and technologies, receive education and training based on the requirements of the time, and engage in physical education and sports.

On February 23, 2018, in order to increase the efficiency and activation of activities related to the education of young people in the spirit of military and patriotism, to more actively involve citizens of our country, state and non-

governmental non-profit organizations and other institutions of civil society in educational and educational activities in this regard, and to inculcate the feelings of patriotism and courage in the minds of young people. With the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers No. 140, the concept of educating youth in the military-patriotic spirit was put into effect.

Because in today's globalization, when the struggle to win the mind and heart of a person is intensifying, it is one of the most important and urgent tasks to protect young people from all kinds of dangers and threats in the international arena, to form their independent opinion, belief and firm position in life.

Indeed, patriotism is a powerful tool that forms in young people a sense of civic duty, personal responsibility, a sense of belonging to the fate of the Motherland, an active life position and firm faith, and professional skills. It requires us to take concrete measures to make our youth ideologically immune to foreign ideas, to strengthen the sense of responsibility for the fate of the Motherland, and to educate them as mature personnel who are devoted to their profession.

Education of young people in the military-patriotic spirit is carried out in the following four stages:

The first stage (ages 3-7) is considered to be the stage in which the first ideas about the surrounding world and the Motherland appear, in which children are taught poems, songs, fairy tales and stories, drawing pictures, military museums and culture and entertainment in family and preschool educational institutions. it includes the formation of feelings of love for the motherland in them based on the introduction of state symbols (flag, coat of arms, anthem);

In the second stage (children aged 7-16) to strengthen students' love and loyalty to the Motherland, to fulfill their filial duty to the Motherland with high responsibility, to strengthen their confidence and positive thoughts in our Armed Forces, to increase the prestige of military service, to make children physically healthy, spiritually mature, good deeds are encouraged, such as formation as a well-rounded person who thinks independently;

the third stage (adolescents aged 16-18 years) is aimed at ensuring mental and physical readiness of young people to serve the Motherland and its defense. The need for physically strong and intellectually mature youth for our national army, the importance of military service, and the reforms carried out in the Armed Forces are given in detail;

The fourth stage (ages 18-30) involves making a significant contribution to the prosperity of the Motherland and the development of the country with the physical and spiritual abilities, leadership skills and intellectual potential of young people, improving their professional qualifications, loyalty and dedication to their profession.

Great work is being done in our country to strengthen the intellectual and creative potential of young people, to increase their involvement in the reforms implemented in our country. Because one of the most important tasks of today is to educate well-rounded, goal-oriented and active young people who have modern knowledge and skills and who can take responsibility for the worthy future of the country.

In accordance with the five important initiatives of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on raising the morale of young people and meaningful organization of their free time, as well as the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to further increase the effectiveness of the work of educating young people in the spirit of patriotism", educating young people in the spirit of national ideals and loyalty to the Motherland, their hearts and the task of organizing measures aimed at instilling in their minds that the protection of the Motherland is an honorable and sacred duty is envisaged.

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